

SYNTHESIS OF *dl*-PINONIC ACID

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The direct total synthesis of *dl*-pinonic acid is effected. This amounts to a new total synthesis of pinocampnone and also of the α - and β -pinenes.

Pinonic acid, the well known oxidation product of α -pinene, has been of more than usual interest. The presence of tetramethylene ring in α -pinene itself was inferred from its constitution. Starting from this acid, Ruzicka and Trebler (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 489) effected a partial synthesis of pinocampnone and thus α - and β -pinenes. The acid itself exhibits mutarotation in its active forms and is very labile (Delépine, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1936, v, 3, 1369). Tiemann (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 3015) claimed to have effected an unusual synthesis of this acid from dihydrodihydroxy- α -campholenic acid involving a contraction of a cyclopentane ring to a cyclobutane ring which was, however, recently disproved by Komppa and Beckmann (*Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 2763). Attempts at synthesis of pinonic acid (I) were also made (i) by Komppa and Klami (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 788) and Guha, Ganapathi and Subramanian (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1505) by means of Arndt and Eistart's reaction (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 200) using diazomethane on *cis*-pinonoyl chloride and (ii) by Guha, Gauapathi and Subramanian (*loc. cit.*) by Blaise's reaction on the acid chloride of 2:2-dimethyl-1-carboxy-cyclobutane-3-acetonitrile. Attempts were also made by the latter authors to synthesise it from pinic acid. Guha and Narasimha Rao (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1591; *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1940, 22A, 317) reported a series of attempts to synthesise it from pinic acid.

Pinonic acid being an oxidation product of α -pinene and pinocampnone (Wallach and Engelbrecht, *Annalen*, 1906, 346, 236) may be taken as synthesised from the elements now that these natural products have been synthesised (Guha and Narasimha Rao, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1940, 22A, 226; Komppa, Klami and Kuvaja, *Chem. Abst.*, 1941, 5878). But this would be more a degradation of the natural products than a real scientific synthesis of pinonic acid from the elements.

The direct total synthesis of pinonic acid has now been accomplished starting from *trans*-pinic acid, synthesised by Guha, Ganapathi, and Subramanian (*loc. cit.*).

Attempts have been made in the past to prepare a suitable derivative of pinic acid such as (II) with a view to applying Blaise-Mair's reaction for the synthesis of a pinonic acid derivative (Guha and Narasimha Rao, *loc. cit.*). This could not be successfully carried out because of the difficulty of effecting a preferential hydrolysis of the ester grouping in compounds of the type (II) (R = .NHPh, -NH.C₆H₄NO₂, and -NH₂X, X = Et).

(I)

(II)

(III)

It has now been found that this difficulty could be overcome by hydrolysing the diphenyl derivative (III, R = CO₂Et), m.p. 99-100°, by means of 95% sulphuric acid and, the acid (III, R = CO₂H), m.p. 139-40°, was obtained in very good yields although the preferential hydrolysis of the ester group in (III, R = CO₂Et) could also be effected, but less readily, by means of castor seed

lipase and 10% alcoholic potash. A Grignard's reaction on the acid chloride of (III, $R=CO_2H$) as is to be expected, went beyond the stage of the formation of the ketone (III, $R=COMe$) but Blaise-Maire's reaction using zinc methyl iodide produced only traces of a ketone (separated and tested by Girard's reagent) giving mainly the methyl ester of (III, $R=CO_2H$). This behaviour of the acid chloride of (III, $R=CO_2H$) towards zinc methyl iodide appears to be very similar to that of benzoyl chloride as observed by Gilman and Gelson (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1936, 56, 518). In view of these circumstances, a reaction was tried using acid chloride of (III, $R=CO_2H$) and cadmium dimethyl (or cadmium methyl halide), and (III, $R=COMe$) was then obtained in about 30% yield. It was characterised by semicarbazone, m.p. 204-205°, identical with a sample prepared from alkali-treated pinonic acid. It gave on hydrolysis pinonic acid (semicarbazone, m.p. 204-5°). The synthetic pinonic acid has been characterised also by its ethyl ester and ethyl ester semicarbazone. All these derivatives are identical with those prepared from an authentic specimen of pinonic acid. On oxidation in the usual manner, *dl*-pinonic acid gave *dl*-pinoylformic acid.

This synthesis of *dl*-pinonic acid amounts to a new total synthesis of pinocampnone and of the pinenes.

EXPERIMENTAL

trans-1-Carboxy-2:2-dimethylcyclobutane-3-acetdiphenylamide (III, $R=CO_2Et$) was prepared from *trans*-1-carboxy-2:2-dimethylcyclobutane-3-acetyl chloride (Guha and Narasimha Rao, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1594) (12 g.), diphenylamine (18.5 g.) and pyridine (30 c.c.). The gummy reaction product was washed free of pyridine with water and dried over sulphuric acid for a week. It was then crystallised from benzene and then several times from alcohol. It separated from alcohol in colourless stout prisms, m.p. 99-100°. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 7.5; N, 3.8. $C_{22}H_{27}O_3N$ requires C, 75.6; H, 7.4; N, 3.8 per cent).

trans-2:2-Dimethylcyclobutane-3-acetdiphenylamide-1-carboxylic acid (III, $R=CO_2H$) was prepared by saponification of the ester (III, $R=CO_2Et$). The hydrolysis with alkali reagents, castor seed lipase and benzene sulphonic acid were unsatisfactory as mixtures of compounds were formed too difficult to separate and the yields of acid (III, $R=CO_2H$) were too low to be of any practical value. The following method gave almost quantitative yield of the acid. The ester (10 g.) and sulphuric acid (95%, 80 c.c.) were heated together at 60-65° for 2½ hours when a homogeneous solution resulted. The product was poured on to crushed ice and the gummy product (which hardened after a while) was separated, washed and purified by dissolving in cold alkali and precipitation with dilute sulphuric acid. The acid was finally crystallised once from benzene and twice from alcohol from which it separated in lustrous prismatic plates or stout prisms, m.p. 139-40°. (Found: C, 74.7; H, 6.8; N, 4.2; Equiv., 337. $C_{21}H_{25}O_3N$ requires C, 74.8; H, 6.8; N, 4.2 per cent. Equiv., 337). The acid on hydrolysis with 15% alcoholic potash for 24 hours gave pinic acid identified as its amide and esterification by alcohol-sulphuric acid method gave back the ester (III, $R=CO_2Et$).

Action of Methyl Magnesium Iodide on the Acid Chloride of (III, $R=CO_2H$).—A Grignard's reagent (1/50 mol.), prepared from magnesium and methyl iodide in the usual manner, was allowed to react with an ethereal solution of acid chloride of (III, $R=CO_2H$) (prepared from 7.1 g. of the acid and thionyl chloride) at 0°. The gummy reaction product, isolated in the usual manner, gave back a small quantity of the acid (III, $R=CO_2H$) but the major portion was neutral. It gave no semicarbazone and when treated with Girard's pyridine reagent, no ketone could be detected. On hydrolysis with 10% methyl alcoholic potash, diphenylamine and 2:2-dimethyl-

cyclobutane-1-dimethylcarbinol-3-acetic acid identified as its ester (Guba and Narasimha Rao, *loc. cit.*) were isolated.

Action of Zinc Methyl Iodide.—A Blaise-Maire's reaction using zinc methyl iodide (from 12 g. of zinc-copper couple and 3 c.c. of methyl iodide) was conducted at 0° in the usual way with the acid chloride of (III, R=CO₂H) (prepared from 14.2 g. of the acid by the thionyl chloride method) dissolved in benzene. As there was no evidence of any reaction, the solution was warmed up to room temperature and kept for a day. Working up in the usual manner, 6 g. of the unchanged acid were recovered while the neutral fraction (A) which partly solidified, was tested for ketones by Girard's pyridine reagent. The aqueous solution of ketonic-Girard reagent complex gave a precipitate with Mayer's alkaloidal reagent and evaporation of the ethereal extract after the removal of non-ketonic bodies gave only a minute amount of a gummy residue. A portion of the neutral fraction (A) was saponified by aqueous alkali and only methyl alcohol and acid (III, R=CO₂H) could be detected in the reaction products.

Attempts to increase the yield of the ketonic fraction by conducting the Blaise-Maire's reaction at the boiling point of benzene were unsuccessful.

trans-dl-Pinonic acid Diphenylamide (III, R=COMe) by the action of Cadmium Methyl Halide on the Acid Chloride of (III, R=COOH).—The Grignard solution (150 c.c.) containing methyl magnesium bromide, prepared from 1 g. of magnesium, was decomposed by finely powdered anhydrous cadmium chloride (7.1 g.) in a manner similar to that described by Gilman and Nelson (*loc. cit.*). An ethereal solution (100 c.c.) containing the acid chloride of (III, R=COOH) (prepared from 10 g. of the acid) was added dropwise with shaking and the reaction was then completed by boiling on the water-bath for 2½ hours. After leaving overnight, it was decomposed with cracked ice and dilute sulphuric acid (10%, 300 c.c.) and thrice extracted with ether. From the ether solution unchanged acid (6.1 g.) was recovered by extracting with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution. After drying over sodium sulphate the ethereal solution was evaporated and the transparent gummy residue was used for further work as it could not be obtained crystalline in contact with the usual solvents. The yield of the product estimated by its semicarbazone is about 30% after allowing for the recovered acid. The semicarbazone of the ketone (III, R=COMe) crystallised from alcohol in slender prismatic plates, m.p. 204.5°. (Found: N, 14.0. C₂₂H₂₈O₂N₄ requires N, 14.3 per cent). The melting point of the semicarbazone was undepressed when admixed with a genuine sample prepared from pinonic acid (*vide infra*).

dl-Pinonic Acid.—The diphenylamide (6.1 g.) and methyl alcoholic potash (10%, 50 c.c.) were boiled under reflux for 24 hours on a steam-bath. After distillation of methyl alcohol, the product was diluted with water (30 c.c.) and extracted with ether to remove diphenylamine. The aqueous solution was acidified with ice-cold 50% sulphuric acid, saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with small portions of chloroform. After washing with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate and drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the chloroform extract was evaporated *in vacuo*. The residue (3 g.), a pale yellow transparent gum, did not solidify when kept in ice-chest under vacuum for over a fortnight.* (Found: *Equiv.*, 185. C₁₀H₁₆O₂ requires *Equiv.*, 184). The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual

* After the paper has been communicated for publication it has been found that *dl*-pinonic acid crystallised slowly after about 2 months. After 3 recrystallisations from water it melted at 103.5° (colourless leaflets) undepressed when admixed with a genuine sample of Bayer's *o*-pinonic acid, m.p. 104.5°. The aqueous mother-liquors gave an oily pinonic acid.

manner and crystallised from alcohol, melted at 205° which remained undepressed when admixed with a genuine sample of *dl*-pinonic acid semicarbazone. (Pinonic acid was prepared for purposes of comparison by treating *cis-dl*-pinonic acid with strong alkali and reprecipitation by acid as described below). The ethyl ester, prepared by alcohol-sulphuric acid method, boiled at $145.6^{\circ}/15$ mm. The ester semicarbazone was found to be identical with a genuine sample of ethyl *dl*-pinonate semicarbazone by mixed melting point method.

Preparation of d-Pinonic Acid Diphenylamide from cis-Pinonic Acid for purposes of comparison with the synthetic sample.—*cis-dl*-Pinonic acid (m.p. 106.7°) (obtained by oxidation of *dl*- α -pinene according to the method of Slawinski and Zacharewicz, *Rocznick. Chem.*, 1934, 14, 213) was purified by once crystallisation from benzene, twice from hot water and twice from methyl alcohol. The acid (5 g.), dissolved in excess of 4*N*-sodium hydroxide, was warmed on the water-bath for 12 hours in order to hasten the isomerisation and establishment of the equilibrium between the *cis* and *trans*-isomers (*cf.* Delépine, *loc. cit.*). After keeping at the room temperature for a day, the chilled alkaline solution was acidified with 6*N*-sulphuric acid, extracted 4 times with chloroform and the extract dried over sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent *in vacuo* a gummy residue was obtained which crystallised rather slowly. The acid mixture (5 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (4 g.) in dry chloroform (15 c.c.) and warmed on the water-bath for 15 minutes. After removal of chloroform and thionyl chloride, the acid chloride, dissolved in benzene (25 c.c.), was poured into a solution of diphenylamine (4.4 g.) in pyridine (20 c.c.). The reaction product after keeping for 1 hour on the water-bath was poured into excess of 2*N*-dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with chloroform. The extract after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was evaporated. The residue, a clear yellow gum, did not solidify in contact with the usual solvents. It was analysed after drying for a week *in vacuo* over sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 4.2. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N$ requires N, 4.2 per cent). The *semicarbazone*, m.p. 205.6° , crystallised in colourless glistening plates. (Found: N, 14.1. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.3 per cent).

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